

To Study Clinical Profile, Risk Factors and Outcome of Cerebral Venous Sinus ThrombosisNitin Shelke¹, Kaustubh Sonawane², Harshal Joshi³, Sanjay Gulhane⁴¹Resident, Department of General Medicine, HBTMC & Dr R N Cooper Hospital, Juhu, Mumbai²Assistant Professor, Department of General Medicine, HBTMC & Dr R N Cooper Hospital, Juhu, Mumbai³Associate Professor, Department of General Medicine, HBTMC & Dr R N Cooper Hospital, Juhu, Mumbai⁴Professor Department of General Medicine, HBTMC & Dr R N Cooper Hospital, Juhu, Mumbai

Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 26-08-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Sanjay Gulhane

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Cerebral venous sinus thrombosis (CVST) refers to occlusion of venous channels in the cranial cavity, including thrombosis of Dural Venous Sinuses or the smaller feeding cerebral veins. It is more prevalent among young to middle-aged people and is more common in females. It is a potentially life-threatening condition requiring early clinical suspicion and prompt treatment.**Material and Methods:** The present prospective observational study was conducted in the Department of General Medicine, HBT medical college and Dr. R.N. Municipal General Hospital, Juhu, Mumbai. The study included confirmed cases of cerebral venous sinus thrombosis based on clinical history and neuroimaging.**Results:** Presentation was acute in 29 (54.72%), subacute in 14 (26.42%) and chronic in 10 (18.87%) cases. Headache (73.58%), focal deficit (56.60%), altered sensorium (52.83%), convulsions (39.62%), fever (28.30%), diplopia (22.64%), papilloedema (37.74%), pallor (41.51%), cranial nerve involvement (24.53%), dehydration (16.98%) and dysphasia (11.32%) was reported among the subjects respectively. Puerperium was the most common identified risk factor seen in 18 (33.96%) followed by Hyper-Homocysteinemia (15.09%) and infection (13.21%).**Conclusions:** Study revealed that focal neurological deficit, altered sensorium and fever at the time of presentation were associated with poor outcome on follow up. No significant association was found with age, sex, seizure at presentation, papilloedema, number of sinuses involved, and parenchymal lesions in brain imaging. Isolated headache at the time of presentation was associated with good prognosis ($p < 0.05$).**Keywords:** CVST, Papilloedema, Headache.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Cerebral venous sinus thrombosis (CVST) refers to occlusion of venous channels in the cranial cavity, including thrombosis of Dural Venous Sinuses or the smaller feeding cerebral veins. Cerebral venous sinus thrombosis (CVST) is more prevalent among young to middle-aged people and is more common in females [1-4]. Although most of the patients have an excellent outcome if treated early and appropriately, delayed diagnosis is often possible due to the broad clinical spectrum of symptoms, varied initial presentation, obscuring of symptoms and signs by the underlying disease like meningitis, and normal findings in neuroimaging [5].

Cerebral venous sinus thrombosis (CVST) is one of the common causes of stroke in young people. Strokes in the young, account for nearly 30% of all cases of stroke in India and cerebral venous sinus

thrombosis (CVST) accounts for 10-20% of these cases. Two-thirds of them develop the same in the postpartum period [6]. Cerebral venous sinus thrombosis (CVST) can be caused by a number of prothrombotic states and disorders of clotting system such as inherited cause is Protein C resistance secondary to Factor V Leiden polymorphism, Protein C and S resistance, and antithrombin III deficiency. Other vasculitis such as Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) and polyarteritis nodosa (PAN) are also relevant in young adults. Dehydration is still the most common cause of puerperal cerebral venous sinus thrombosis (CVST) in our country [6].

Animal model studies have shown that sinus thrombosis leads to sinus occlusion and backflow of blood into venules and capillaries, resulting in

increased local pressure, eventually resulting in massive cerebral edema [7]. Decrease in the cerebrospinal fluid drainage due to sinus occlusion can result from the dysfunction of arachnoid granulations, causing an increase in intracranial pressure. A continuous rise in pressure results in capillary hypertension, cerebral edema, and venous haemorrhage [8]. Treatment modalities may include anticoagulation or thrombolytic therapy. Anticoagulant therapy includes heparin and warfarin.

Aims and Objective: To study clinical profile, risk factors and outcome in patients of Cerebral Venous Sinus Thrombosis (CVST).

Material and Methods

Type of Study & Study Area: The present prospective observational study was conducted in the Department of General Medicine, HBT medical college and Dr. R.N. Municipal general hospital, Juhu, Mumbai. The study included confirmed cases of Cerebral Venous Sinus Thrombosis based on clinical history and neuroimaging. Before the commencement of the study, ethical permission was taken from the ethical committee of the institute. Subjects were recruited after obtaining consent from themselves/guardians.

Inclusion Criteria

- All confirmed cases of cerebral venous sinus thrombosis.
- Patients having age between 12-60 years.
- Patients/guardians who gave consent for the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients who were initially diagnosed as cerebral venous sinus thrombosis, but MRV/ Angiogram was normal.
- Patients having age <12 years.
- Pregnant women.

Method of Collecting Data

The study was conducted on 53 patients of cerebral venous thrombosis. The diagnosis of Cerebral Venous Sinus Thrombosis was based on appropriate clinical findings supported by radiological evidence of Cerebral Venous Sinus Thrombosis.

Radiological diagnosis was based on established radiological criteria. In all the 53 patients detailed history including demographic factors, type and duration of symptoms, onset of symptoms: acute (<48 h), subacute (48 h to <30 days), and chronic (>30 days), features suggestive of etiological factors, personal habits, comorbid illnesses, detailed menstrual and obstetric history in case of females were noted in case research. All the patients were subjected to detailed clinical

examination including general, neurological and other systems examination.

Investigations like complete blood count, erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR), blood urea, blood sugar, serum creatinine, serum electrolytes, lipid profile, X-ray chest, Electrocardiogram, Elisa for Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV), VDRL, coagulation profile including bleeding time, clotting time, prothrombin time, activated partial thromboplastin time were done in all patients. Specific investigations like antinuclear antibody (ANA), antiphospholipid antibodies, tests for procoagulant states like protein C, protein S, antithrombin III (AT III) and serum homocysteine with an aim to detect the underlying etiology were done in certain patients as indicated. Outcome at the end of the hospital stay was recorded in all patients. The modified Rankin score was used for outcome assessment. The modified Rankin Scale (mRS) is commonly used for expressing the degree of disability of post stroke patients as well as those with other neurological disability.

Statistical Analysis

All the collected data was entered in Microsoft Excel sheet and then transferred to SPSS software ver. 17 for analysis. Qualitative data was presented as frequency and percentages and analyzed using chi-square test. Quantitative data was presented as mean and SD and compared by t-test. P-value < 0.05 was taken as level of significance.

Results

Out of 53 cases 17 (32.08%) were males and 36 (67.92%) were females (table 1, graph 1). Table 2, graph 2 shows the age distribution among the study subjects. 7.55%, 60.38%, 16.98% and 15.09% of the subjects were having 12-20, 21-30, 31-40 and 41-60 years age respectively. Presentation was acute in 29 (54.72%), subacute in 14 (26.42%) and chronic in 10 (18.87%) cases as shown in table 3, graph 3. Table 4, graph 4 shows the neurological symptoms and signs among the study subjects. Headache (73.58%), focal deficit (56.60%), altered sensorium (52.83%), convulsions (39.62%), fever (28.30%), diplopia (22.64%), papilloedema (37.74%), pallor (41.51%), cranial nerve involvement (24.53%), dehydration (16.98%) and dysphasia (11.32%) were reported among the subjects respectively.

Hence headache was the most common symptom while papilloedema was the most common neurological sign. Table 5, graph 5 shows the predisposing conditions among the study subjects. Puerperium was the most common identified risk factor seen in 18 (33.96%) followed by hyperhomocysteine (15.09%) and infection (13.21%). Least common identified risk factor was APLA as well as recent surgery. No possible cause could be found in 8 (15.09%) patients.

Location of brain parenchymal lesions and sinus involvement is summarized in Table 6, graph 6a, b. Fronto-parietal was the most common location followed by parietal, temporoparietal as well as fronto-temporo-parietal. Most common sinus involved was transverse sinus (64.15%) followed by superior sagittal sinus (60.38%) and sigmoid sinus (35.85%) while the least common sinus involved was cavernous as well as cortical vein. All 53 patients were given anticoagulation, initially with LMWH followed by OAC. Additional treatment included antiepileptics in 26 (49.06%) patients and antiedema measures in 30 (56.60%) patients and decompressive craniotomy was done in 1 patient.

Information on outcome was available for all patients at the time of discharge. After three and six

months, poor outcome ($mRS \geq 3$) was revealed among 26.42% and 22.64% of the subjects respectively (table 7, graph 7). Chi square test analysis revealed that focal neurological deficit, altered sensorium and fever at the time of presentation were associated with poor outcome on follow up. No significant association was found with age, sex, seizure at presentation, papilloedema, number of sinuses involved, and parenchymal lesions in brain imaging.

Isolated headache at the time of presentation was associated with good prognosis ($p < 0.05$). During the follow up period of 6 months, none of the patients had any repeat thrombotic event while 1 patient had seizure recurrence (table 8).

Table 1: Gender distribution among the study subjects

Gender	N	%
Male	17	32.08
Female	36	67.92
Total	53	100.00

Table 2: Age distribution among the study subjects

Age Group (in years)	N	%
12-20	4	7.55
21-30	32	60.38
31-40	9	16.98
41-60	8	15.09
Total	53	100.00

Table 3: Presentation among the study subjects

Presentation	N	%
Acute	29	54.72
Subacute	14	26.42
Chronic	10	18.87
Total	53	100.00

Table 4: Neurological symptoms and signs among the study subjects

Symptom and Sign	N	%
Headache	39	73.58
Focal deficit	30	56.60
Altered sensorium	28	52.83
Convulsions	21	39.62
Fever	15	28.30
Diplopia	12	22.64
Papilloedema	22	41.51
Pallor	20	37.74
Cranial nerve involvement	13	24.53
Dehydration	9	16.98
Dysphasia	6	11.32

Table 5: Predisposing conditions among the study subjects

Predisposing condition	N	%
Perpeurium	18	33.96
Infection	7	13.21
Hyperhomocysteine	8	15.09
Protein C deficiency	4	7.55
Protein S deficiency	2	3.77
APLA	1	1.89

OCP	2	3.77
Recent Surgery	1	1.89
PNH	2	3.77
No cause	8	15.09

Table 6: CT Brain and MRI brain findings among the study subjects

Location of brain parenchymal lesion (In Imaging)	N	%
No lesion	12	22.64
Parietal	6	11.32
Fronto-parietal	7	13.21
Frontal	5	9.43
Temporoparietal	6	11.32
Fronto-temporo-parietal	6	11.32
Temporo-parieto-occipital	5	9.43
Temporo-occipital	2	3.77
Occipital	2	3.77
Diffuse	2	3.77
Sinus involved		
Transverse sinus	34	64.15
Superior sagittal sinus	32	60.38
Sigmoid sinus	19	35.85
Jugular sinus	7	13.21
Straight sinus	6	11.32
Internal cerebral vein	3	5.66
Cavernous sinus	1	1.89
Cortical vein (Vein of labbe)	1	1.89

Table 7: mRS at different follow up among the study subjects

Time Interval	mRS			
	Poor Outcome (≥ 3)		Good Outcome (0-2)	
	N	%	N	%
After 3 Month	14	26.42	39	73.58
After 6 Month	12	22.64	41	77.36

Table 8: Prognostic factors on follow up

Time Interval	3 Month			6 Month		
	Poor Outcome (≥ 3): 14	Good Outcome (0-2): 39	p value	Poor Outcome (≥ 3): 12	Good Outcome (0-2): 41	p value
Gender						
Male	5	12	0.32	3	9	0.21
Female	9	27		9	27	
Age Group						
≤ 30	8	28	0.30	7	29	0.12
> 30	6	11		7	10	
Focal deficit						
Present	13	17	$< 0.01^{**}$	12	18	$< 0.01^{**}$
Absent	1	22		0	23	
Altered Sensorium						
Present	14	14	$< 0.01^{**}$	12	16	$< 0.01^{**}$
Absent	0	25		0	25	
Convulsions						
Present	8	13	0.29	7	14	0.34
Absent	6	26		5	27	
Fever						
Present	9	6	0.03*	9	6	0.016*
Absent	5	33		3	35	
Papilloedema						
Present	6	14	0.11	5	15	0.10

Absent	8	25		7	26	
Headache						
Present	9	30	0.041*	7	32	0.13
Absent	5	9		5	9	

** : highly significant, * : significant

Graph 1: Gender distribution among the study subjects

Graph 2: Age distribution among the study subjects

Graph 3: Presentation among the study subjects

Graph 4: Neurological symptoms and signs among the study subjects

Graph 5: Predisposing conditions among the study subjects

Graph 6a: Location of brain parenchymal lesion (In Imaging)

Graph 6 (b): Sinus involvement among the study subjects

Graph 7: mRS at different follow up among the study subjects

Discussion

Gender

Though cerebral venous sinus thrombosis can occur at any time from infancy to old age, most reported modern cases have been in adult women in association with puerperium [12].

It is more common in females than in males [13]. In this study, out of 53 cases 17 (32.08%) were

males and 36 (67.92%) were females. Hence there were more females as compared to males. Similarly, Kapinder Yadav et al [11] in their study reported female dominance with a M:F ratio of 1:3.3. International Study of Cerebral Vein and Dural Sinus Thrombosis (ISCVST) reported a M:F ratio of 1:2.9. In contrary, Narayan et al observed a higher male: female ratio of 1.17:1 [10].

Age Group

It is a disease of children and young adults 58.0%, 7.55%, 60.38%, 16.98% and 15.09% of the subjects were having 12-20, 21-30, 31-40 and 41-60 years age respectively. Hence majority of the subjects were from 21-30 years of age group in this study. In the largest clinical series, the International Study on Cerebral vein and dural sinus thrombosis (ISCVT), the median age of patients with cerebral venous sinus thrombosis was 37 years [13] and in a study conducted in Pakistan by Khealani et al [14] median age was 35 years compared to the median age in our study of 28 years. Hence a lower median age was observed in our study compared to most other studies [14,15]. This could be because 60.38% of our patients were between the age range of 21-30 years of which majority were females.

Presentation

According to literature, in $\geq 50\%$ of the patients, the onset is subacute. Narayan et al [10] too reported similar findings as revealed in the present study. In a study by Kapinder Yadav et al [11], acute, subacute and chronic presentation was found among 14 (46.7%), 10 (33.3%) and 6 (20%) subjects respectively.

Neurological Symptoms and Signs

Headache (73.58%) was the most common symptom while papilloedema was the most common neurological sign in present study. Kapinder Yadav et al [11] in their study reported that headache was the most common symptom, present in 22 (73.3%) patients. Papilloedema was the most common neurological sign, seen in 14 (46.7%) patients. As far as the presenting symptoms are concerned, up to 90% of patients with cerebral venous sinus thrombosis, complained of headache which is the most frequent symptom and often the initial one. By ISCVST, headache was the only symptom in 9% of patients with cerebral venous sinus thrombosis [16]. Altered sensorium was observed in about 52.83% of patients which is little higher as observed by Khealani et al (37%) [14]. Seizures are more frequent in cerebral venous sinus thrombosis than in other stroke types [16]. About 30 to 40% of patients present with seizures, either focal or generalized or with status epilepticus [17,18]. Seizures was observed in 39.62% of our patients however seizure incidence was slightly higher in other studies [10,14,19]. Comparison of the common clinical presentations in our study with other studies is shown in the table [9].

Risk Factors

In the present study, puerperium was the most common identified risk factor seen in 18 (33.96%) followed by hyperhomocysteine (15.09%) and infection (13.21%). Least common identified risk factor was APLA as well as recent surgery. No

possible cause could be found in 8 (15.09%) patients. Puerperium as a cause of cerebral venous sinus thrombosis has been reported in lesser frequencies in western studies [20,21], however a very high proportion of puerperal cerebral venous sinus thrombosis was seen in Indian studies done in past [22,23]. The decrease in puerperal cerebral venous sinus thrombosis in present study reflects improved obstetric care in India.

In 2004 Cantu et al [24] reported a correlation of high plasma concentrations of homocysteine and low plasma folate levels and cerebral venous sinus thrombosis in increased frequency in Mexican population owing to low socioeconomic conditions and deficient nutritional status. Infection accounted for 13.21% of cerebral venous sinus thrombosis cases in present study similar to 12% seen in ISCVST. We could not find any cause for cerebral venous sinus thrombosis in 15.09% of our patients. Similar findings were too reported by Kapinder Yadav et al [11] in their study.

Though peripartum cerebral venous sinus thrombosis is especially common in less developed world [25], there is a difference among different developing countries. For example, Daif et al [26] from Saudi Arabia reported only 1 out of 40 patients being in postpartum state and a very lower incidence of peripartum cerebral venous sinus thrombosis was also reported in the Iranian study by Ashjazadeh et al [19] and the study done in Hyderabad, India by Narayan et al [10]. However, in present study puerperium was the leading cause of cerebral venous sinus thrombosis.

Douglas et al [27] reported by multivariate analysis that caesarean section and hypertension was significantly associated with peripartum and postpartum cerebral venous sinus thrombosis. The authors of the study suggest that the small increased risk with pregnancy induced hypertension might be due to a higher rate of caesarian section in women with hypertension and that there may be a cumulative effect of resistance to activated protein C during pregnancy together with decreased protein C levels following surgery [28,29].

Location of brain parenchymal lesions and sinus involvement

Fronto-parietal was the most common location followed by parietal, temporoparietal as well as fronto-temporo-parietal. Most common sinus involved was transverse sinus (64.15%) followed by superior sagittal sinus (60.38%) and sigmoid sinus (35.85%) while the least common sinus involved was cavernous as well as cortical vein in present study. The present study like other studies confirms that superior sagittal sinus and transverse sinus, with or without involvement of other sinuses, are most common sinus involved [10,26].

Outcome and its Associated Factors

All 53 patients were given anticoagulation, initially with LMWH followed by OAC (warfarin). Additional treatment included antiepileptics in 26 (49.06%) patients and antiedema measures in 30 (56.60%) patients and decompressive craniotomy was done in 1 patient.

Information on outcome was available for all patients at the time of discharge. After three and six months, poor outcome ($mRS \geq 3$) was revealed among 26.42% and 22.64% of the subjects respectively. An attempt was made to correlate clinical profile with the site of venous occlusion but no significant clinical pattern was found with mode of onset, clinical parameters and outcome whether sinuses alone, deep sinuses and combination of sinuses and veins.

Chi square test analysis revealed that focal neurological deficit, altered sensorium and fever at the time of presentation were associated with poor outcome on follow up. No significant association was found with age, sex, seizure at presentation, papilloedema, number of sinuses involved, and parenchymal lesions in brain imaging. Isolated headache at the time of presentation was associated with good prognosis ($p < 0.05$). During the follow up period of 6 months, none of the patients had any repeat thrombotic event while 1 patient had seizure recurrence.

Similarly Kapinder Yadav et al [11] in their study found that there was no correlation between clinical profile and topographic radiological findings, like involvement of superficial/deep venous system or the pattern of infarction, to evolve a pattern of diagnostic significance. In ISCVST3 age > 37 years, male sex, any malignancy, CNS infection, seizures, mental status disorders, intra cerebral haemorrhage and deep venous system thrombosis were associated with poor prognosis. Coma and intra cerebral haemorrhage were associated with poor prognosis in a study by Bruijn et al [20]. Identification of high-risk patient is important because they can be benefited by more aggressive therapeutic interventions [11].

Limitations

Because of resource limitations, the evaluation of genetic prothrombotic factors and uncommon hematological conditions were not possible to evaluate. Another important limitation of present study is small sample size.

Summary

- Gender distribution among the study subjects showed out of 53 cases 17 (32.08%) were males and 36 (67.92%) were females.
- It is a disease of children and young adults, in present study 60.38% patients were between

the age range of 21-30 years of which majority were females.

- Presentation was acute (54.72%), subacute (26.42%) and chronic (18.87%) in present study.
- Headache (73.58%), focal deficit (56.60%), altered sensorium (52.83%), convulsions (39.62%), fever (28.30%), diplopia (22.64%), papilloedema (37.74%), pallor (41.51%), cranial nerve involvement (24.53%), dehydration (16.98%) and dysphasia (11.32%) was reported among the subjects respectively. Hence headache was the most common symptom while papilloedema was the most common neurological sign.
- Puerperium was the most common identified risk factor seen in (33.96%) followed by hyperhomocysteine (15.09%) and infection (13.21%). Least common identified risk factor was APLA as well as recent surgery.
- No possible cause could be found in 8 (15.09%) patients.
- Fronto-parietal was the most common location followed by parietal, temporoparietal as well as fronto-temporo-parietal. Most common sinus involved was transverse sinus (64.15%) followed by superior sagittal sinus (60.38%) and sigmoid sinus (35.85%) while the least common sinus involved was cavernous as well as cortical vein.
- All 53 patients were given anticoagulation, initially with LMWH followed by Oral Anticoagulants. After three and six months, poor outcome ($mRS \geq 3$) was revealed among 26.42% and 22.64% of the subjects respectively.
- Focal neurological deficit altered sensorium and fever at the time of presentation were associated with poor outcome on follow up.
- No significant association was found with age, sex, seizure at presentation, papilloedema, number of sinuses involved, and parenchymal lesions in brain imaging.
- Isolated headache at the time of presentation was associated with good prognosis ($p < 0.05$). During the follow up period of 6 months, none of the patients had any repeat thrombotic event while 1 patient had seizure recurrence (table 8).

Conclusion

- Cerebral venous sinus thrombosis (CVST) is more prevalent among young to middle-aged people and is more common in females. It is a potentially life-threatening condition requiring early clinical suspicion and prompt treatment.
- Puerperium was the most common identified risk factor seen followed by hyperhomocysteine, infection. Least common identified risk factor was APLA as well as recent surgery.

- No significant association was found with age, sex, seizure at presentation, papilloedema, number of sinuses involved, and parenchymal lesions in brain imaging.
- Focal neurological deficit altered sensorium and fever at the time of presentation were associated with poor outcome on follow up.

References

1. Bousser MG, Ferro JM. Cerebral venous thrombosis: An update. *Lancet Neurol* 2007; 6:162-70.
2. Bhojo AK, Mohammad W, Mohammed S, Erum S, Shahid MF, Ayeesha KK. Cerebral venous thrombosis: A descriptive multicenter study of patients in Pakistan and Middle East. *Stroke* 2008; 39:2707-11.
3. Bansal BC, Gupta RR, Prakash C. Stroke during pregnancy and puerperium in young females below the age of 40 years as a result of cerebral venous/ venous sinus thrombosis. *Jpn Heart J* 1980; 21:171-83.
4. Bousser MG. Cerebral venous thrombosis: Diagnosis and management. *J Neurol* 2000; 247:252-8.
5. Raj AT, Kiruthika R, Sowthariya R. Study of Clinical and Radiological Presentation of Cerebral Venous Thrombosis and its Outcome – A Prospective Study. *Int J Sci Stud* 2021; 8(10):151-157.
6. Patil VC, Choraria K, Desai N, Agrawal S. Clinical profile and outcome of cerebral venous sinus thrombosis at tertiary care center. *J Neurosci Rural Pract* 2014; 5:218-24
7. Röttger C, Bachmann G, Gerriets T, Kaps M, Kuchelmeister K, Schachenmayr W, et al. A new model of reversible sinus sagittalis superior thrombosis in the rat: magnetic resonance imaging changes. *Neurosurgery*. 2005; 57(3):573–80.
8. Ueda K, Nakase H, Miyamoto K, Otsuka H, Sakaki T. Impact of anatomical difference of the cerebral venous system on microcirculation in a gerbil superior sagittal sinus occlusion model. *Acta Neurochir*. 2000; 142(1):75–82.
9. Villringer A, Seiderer M, Bauer WM et al. Diagnosis of superior sagittal sinus thrombosis by three-dimensional magnetic resonance flow imaging. *Lancet* 1989; 1:1086-1087.
10. Narayan D, Kaul S, Ravishankar K, Suryaprabha T, Bandaru VS, Mridula KR, Jabeen SA, Alladi S, Meena AK, Borgohain R. Risk factors, clinical profile, and long-term outcome of 428 patients of cerebral sinus venous thrombosis: Insights from Nizam's Institute Venous Stroke Registry, Hyderabad (India). *Neurol Ind*. 2012; 60(2):154-159.
11. Yadav K, Dabla S, Sharma B, Yadav P, Kumar S, Juneja H. A Study of Clinical Profile, Risk Factors and Outcome in Patients of Cerebral Venous Sinus Thrombosis. *SSRG Int J Med Sci* .2016; 3(12):73-3.
12. Bhojo AK, Mohammad W, Mohammed S, Erum S, Shahid MFSK, Ayeesha KK Cerebral venous thrombosis: a descriptive multicenter study of patients in Pakistan and Middle East. *Stroke* 2008; 39:2707–11.
13. Paulo PC, Gustavo M de C, Antonio PGN. Cerebral venous sinus thrombosis: study of fifteen cases and literature review. *Rev Assoc Med Bras* 2010; 56(3):288–92.
14. Jose MF. Cerebral venous thrombosis. Mohr, Wolf, Gotta, Moskowitz, Maylery, Von kummer,(eds). *Stroke*, 5th ed. chapter 28, pp. 516–30.
15. Tanislav C, Siekmann R, Sieweke N, et al. Cerebral venous thrombosis: clinical manifestations and diagnosis. *BMC Neurol* 2011; 11:69.
16. Ferro JM, Canhao P, Stam J, et al. Early seizures in cerebral vein and dural sinus thrombosis: risk factors and role of antiepileptics. *Stroke* 2008;39:1152–8.
17. Nahid A, Afshin BH, Maryam P, Hoseinjan A. Cerebral venous-sinus thrombosis: A case series analysis. *Iran J Med Sci* 2011; 36(3):178–82.
18. de Bruijn S, de Haan R, Stan J. Clinical features and prognostic factors of cerebral venous thrombosis in a prospective series of 59 patients. *J Neurol Neurosurg Psychiatr* 2001; 70:105–08.
19. Deschiens M, Conard J, Horellou M, Ameri A, Preter M, Chedu F. Coagulation studies, factor V Leiden and anticardiolipin antibodies in 40 cases of cerebral venous sinus thrombosis. *Stroke* 1996; 27:1724–30.
20. Nagaraja D, Sarma GR. Treatment of cerebral sinus/venous thrombosis. *Neurol India* 2002; 50:114.
21. Nagpal RD. Dural sinus and cerebral venous thrombosis. *Neurosurg Review* 1983; 6:155-60.
22. Cantu C, Alonso E, Jara A, Martinez L, Rios C, Fernandez MA et al. Hyperhomocysteinemia, low Folate and vitamin B12 concentrations, and methylene tetrahydrofolate reductase mutation in cerebral venous thrombosis. *Stroke* 2004; 35:1790- 94.
23. Canhao P, Bousser MG, Bariagarrementeria F, et al. ISCVT collaborators: predisposing conditions for cerebral vein thrombosis. *J Neurol* 2002; 249:52.
24. Daif A, Awada A, al-Rajeh S, et al. Cerebral venous thrombosis in adults: a study of 40 cases from Saudi Arabia. *Stroke* 1995; 26:1193–5.
25. Douglas JL, Richard JK. Risk factors for peripartum and postpartum stroke and intracranial venous thrombosis. *Stroke* 2000; 31:1274–82.
26. Cumming AM, Tait RC, Fildes S, et al. Development of resistance to activated protein C

during pregnancy. Br J Haematol 1995; 90:725-7.

27. Griffin JH, Mosher DF, Zimmerman T, Kleiss AJ. Protein C and anti-thrombotic protein is

reduced in hospitalised patients with intravascular coagulation. Blood 1982; 60:261-9.